

Supplementary Materials for Direct N-alkylation of unprotected amino acids with alcohols

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Experimental section

table S1. Optimization of reaction conditions for the direct N-ethylation of unprotected amino acids (1a to 1i) with ethanol (2a).

Entry	1	T. [h]	Temp. [°C]	Conv. 1 [%] ^a	Sel. 3 [%] ^a	ee [%] ^b
1	1a L-Proline	18	110	>99	3aa >99 (99)	n.d.
2	1a L-Proline	18	90	>99	3aa >99 (99)	93
3	1a L-Proline	18	60	53	3aa 53	n.d.
4	1b Glycine	18	90	>99	3ba >99	/
5	1c L-Alanine	18	90	>99	3ca >99	84
6	1c L-Alanine	47	60	>99	3ca >99	86
7	1d L-Valine	18	90	>99	3da 55	n.d.
8	1d L-Valine	24	90	>99	3da >99	>99
9	1e L-Leucine	18	90	>99	3ea >99 (99)	99
10	1f L-Phenylalanine	18	90	>99	3fa >99	97 ^c
11	1g L-Serine	18	90	>99	3ga >99	86
12	1h Lysine	18	90	<1%	3ha /	/
13 ^d	1h Lysine	18	100	<1%	3ha /	/
14	1i N ⁶ -Ac-lysine	18	90	>99	3ia <5%	/
15 ^d	1i N ⁶ -Ac-lysine	18	90	>99	3ia (74)	n.d.

General procedure see MATERIALS AND METHODS, isolated yields in parenthesis.

^aConversion and selectivity are based on ¹H NMR; ^bee was determined by HPLC measurement, through the corresponding amino acid amide, unless otherwise specified, see page S22 for details of ee determination; ^cee was measured by HPLC measurement, through corresponding amino acid methyl ester; ^d1 ml CF₃CH₂OH was added.

table S2. Direct mono-N-isopropylation of an amino acid (1) with isopropanol (2b).

Entry	1 [mmol]	Sol. [ml]	T. [h]	Conv. 1 [%] ^a	Sel. 3 [%] ^a
1	1a Proline	/	18	>99	3ab >99 (99)
3	1f Phenylalanine	/	18	<5	n.d.
4	1f Phenylalanine	H ₂ O 0.5	45	<1	n.d.
5	1f Phenylalanine	2c 0.5	45	15	n.d.
6	1f Phenylalanine	2c 1	18	12	n.d.
7 ^c	1f Phenylalanine	2c 1	18	85	n.d.
8	1f Phenylalanine	2c 2	18	10	n.d.
9	1f Phenylalanine	2d 1	24	>99	3fb >99 (99)
10	1e Leucine	/	18	<5	n.d.
11	1e Leucine	2d 1	24	40	n.d.
12 ^c	1e Leucine	2d 1	28	>99	3eb >99 (99)
13	1d Valine	/	18	<5	n.d.
14	1d Valine	2d 1	24	>99	3db >99 (99)
15	1g Serine	/	18	<5	n.d.
16	1g Serine	2d 1	24	15	n.d.
17 ^b	1g Serine	2d 1	24	40	n.d.
18 ^c	1g Serine	2d 1	24	>99	3gb >99 (99)
19	1c Alanine	/	18	<5	n.d.
20	1c Alanine	2d 1	24	67	n.d.
21	1c Alanine	2d 1	28	>99	3cb >99 (99)

General procedure (see MATERIALS AND METHODS), isolated yields in parenthesis. ^aConversion and selectivity are based on ¹H NMR; ^b2 mol% **Cat 1** was used; ^c100 °C.

table S3. Direct N-alkylation of a free amino acid (1) with various alcohols (2).

Entry	1 [mmol]	2	Sol. [ml]	T. [h]	Conv. 1 [%] ^a	Sel. 3 [%] ^a
1	1a Proline / 0.2	2c MeOH / 2 ml	/	18	<1	3ac /
2	1a Proline / 0.2	2d CF ₃ CH ₂ OH / 2 ml	/	18	<1	3ad /
3	1a Proline / 0.2	2e <i>n</i> BuOH / 2 ml	/	24	>99	3ae >99
4	1a Proline / 0.5	2f / 5 ml	/	18	>99	3af (55)
5	1a Proline / 0.2	2g / 2 ml	/	18	>99	3ag (71)
6	1a Proline / 0.2	2h BnOH / 2 ml	/	18	>99	3ah (68)
7	1a Proline / 0.5	2i / 2 mmol	2d /tol. 1/4	20	>99	3ai (82)
8	1f Phenylalanine / 0.5	2e <i>n</i> BuOH / 4 ml	2d 2	24	>99	3fe (84)
9	1f Phenylalanine / 0.5	2j 1-nonanol / 1 ml	2d /tol 2/2	24	>99	3fj (75)
10 ^b	1f Phenylalanine / 0.2	2k 1,5-pentanediol / 2 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	18	>99	3fk (35)
12	1b Glycine / 0.5	2h BnOH / 2 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	18	/	3bh (52)
13	1b Glycine / 0.5	2j 1-nonanol / 2 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	24	>99	3bj (91)
14	1b Glycine / 0.2	2l 2-butanol / 4 ml	2d 1	24	>99	3bl >99
15	1b Glycine / 0.5	2m 1-pentanol / 2 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	18	>99	3bm (90)
16	1b Glycine / 0.5	2m 1-pentanol / 0.6 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	18	>99	3bm' (46) 3bm (29)
17	1b Glycine / 0.5	2n 1-dodecanol / 2 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	18	>99	3bn (92)

General procedure (see MATERIALS AND METHODS), isolated yields in parenthesis. ^aConversion and selectivity are based on ¹H NMR; ^b100 °C.

table S4. Direct N-alkylation of di- and tripeptides (4a to 4b) with alcohols (2).

Entry	4 [mmol]	2	Sol. [ml]	T. [h]	Conv. 4 [%] ^a	Sel. 5 [%] ^a
1	4a / 0.2	2a ethanol / 5 ml	/	24	>95	5aa (>95)
2	4a / 0.5	2k 1,5-pentanediol / 2 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	24	n.d.	5ak (36)
3	4a / 0.5	2n 1-dodecanol / 0.6 mmol	2d /tol 2/3	18	n.d.	5an (58)
4	4a / 0.5	2n 1-dodecanol / 2 mmol	2d 2	24	n.d.	5an (82)
5	4b / 0.2	2a ethanol / 5 ml	/	24	n.d.	5ba (50)
6	4b / 0.5	2a ethanol / 5 ml	2d 2	18	n.d.	5ba (67)

General procedure (see MATERIALS AND METHODS), isolated yields in parenthesis. ^aConversion and selectivity are based on ¹H NMR.

table S5. Iron-catalyzed N-ethylation of amino acids with ethanol (2a).

Entry	1 [mmol]	Cat [mol %]	2a [ml]	T. [h]	Temp. [°C]	Conv. 1 [%] ^a	Sel. 3 [%] ^a	ee [%] ^b
1	1a / 0.5	Cat 2a / 4, Me ₃ NO / 8	2	18	110	>99	>99	n.d.
2	1a / 0.5	Cat 2a / 4, Me ₃ NO / 8	2	16	90	>99	>99 (99)	94
3	1a / 0.5	Cat 2a / 2, Me ₃ NO / 4	2	16	80	14	14	n.d.
4	1e / 0.5	Cat 2a / 4, Me ₃ NO / 8	4	15	90	15	n.d.	/
5	1e / 0.2	Cat 2a / 10, Me ₃ NO / 20	5	24	90	60	n.d.	/
6	1e / 0.2	Cat 2a / 10, Me ₃ NO / 20	5	18	110	70	n.d.	/
7 ^b	1e / 0.5	Cat 2a / 4, Me ₃ NO / 8	4	24	100	30	n.d.	/
8 ^b	1e / 0.5	Cat 2 / 4	4	24	100	70	n.d.	/
9 ^c	1e / 0.5	Cat 2 / 4	4	24	110	18	n.d.	/
10 ^b	1e / 0.5	Cat 2 / 4	4	24	110	90	n.d.	/
11 ^b	1e / 0.5	Cat 2 / 4	4	42	110	>95	(49)	80
12 ^b	1f / 0.5	Cat 2 / 4	4	42	110	>95	(55)	72

General procedure (see MATERIALS AND METHODS), isolated yields in parenthesis. ^aConversion and selectivity are based on ¹H NMR; ^b1 ml CF₃CH₂OH was added; ^c1 ml H₂O was added.

table S6. Iron-catalyzed N-alkylation of unprotected amino acids (1a to 1c) with long-chain aliphatic alcohols (2) to produce surfactants.

Entry	1	2	Yield 3 [%]
1	1b Glycine	2n 1-dodecanol / 1 ml	3bn' 54 3bn 8
2	1b Glycine	2j 1-nonanol / 1 ml	3bj' 53
3	1b Glycine	2o 1-decanol / 1 ml	3bo' 69
4 ^a	1b Glycine	2p 1-tetradecanol / 2 mmol	3bp' 32
4 ^a	1b Glycine	2q 1-hexadecanol / 2 mmol	3bq' 38
5 ^a	1b Glycine	2r 1-octadecanol / 2 mmol	3br' 39
6	1c Alanine	2n 1-dodecanol / 1 ml	3cn' 49
7	1a Proline	2j 1-nonanol / 1 ml	3aj 52

General procedure (see MATERIALS AND METHODS), isolated yields are shown.

^aThe products were isolated as corresponding amino acid methyl esters.

Spectral data of isolated compounds

N-ethyl-proline (3aa): Synthesized according to the **General procedure**. The product was obtained in quantitative yield according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.83 – 3.96 (m, 1H), 3.64 – 3.78 (m, 1H), 3.15 – 3.33 (m, 2H), 3.05 – 3.15 (m, 1H), 2.35 – 2.52 (m, 1H), 1.99 – 2.16 (m, 2H), 1.85 – 1.99 (m, 1H), 1.27 (t, J = 7.28 Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, MeOD) δ 173.46, 70.13, 55.45, 51.51, 30.32, 24.34, 11.31. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 144.10191; found: 144.10181. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (21)

N,N-di-ethyl-glycine (3ba): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.66 (s, 2H), 3.22 (q, J = 7.31 Hz, 4H), 1.26 (t, J = 7.32 Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 173.50, 57.36, 52.14, 11.13. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 132.10191; found: 132.10180. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (8)

N,N-di-ethyl-alanine (3ca): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.77 – 3.92 (m, 1H), 3.19 – 3.39 (m, 2H), 3.00 – 3.20 (m, 2H), 1.38 – 1.52 (m, 3H), 1.17 – 1.37 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 174.31, 61.46, 47.04, 44.97, 11.47, 9.29, 8.32. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 146.11756; found: 146.11746.

***N,N*-di-ethyl-valine (3da):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.45 – 3.52 (m, 1H) 3.05 – 3.35 (m, 4H), 2.22 – 2.40 (m, 1H), 1.15 – 1.40 (m, 6H), 0.99 – 1.10 (m, 3H), 0.86 – 0.99 (m, 3H) ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 174.31, 74.85, 49.85, 45.30, 28.02, 22.22, 18.81, 11.73, 9.62. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 174.14886; found: 174.14879.

***N,N*-di-ethyl-leucine (3ea):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.58 – 3.67 (m, 1H), 3.08 – 3.30 (m, 4H), 1.67 – 1.78 (m, 1H), 1.51 – 1.67 (m, 2H), 1.26 (t, $J = 5.24$ Hz, 6H), 0.83 – 1.00 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 176.34, 68.56, 48.14 (br.s), 38.83, 27.77, 25.52, 23.04, 11.13 (br.s). HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$: 186.14886; found: 186.15012.

***N,N*-di-ethyl-phenylalanine (3fa):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 7.12 – 7.43 (m, 5H), 3.80 – 3.93 (m, 1H), 3.08 – 3.40 (m, 4H), 2.98 – 3.31 (m, 2H), 1.17 – 1.33 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 172.37, 135.44, 129.06, 128.80, 127.28, 67.81, 45.70 (br.s), 33.44, 8.42 (br.s). HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$: 220.13321; found: 220.13433.

***N,N*-di-ethyl-serine (3ga)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.98 – 4.18 (m, 2H), 3.79 – 3.91 (m, 1H), 3.37 – 3.52 (m, 1H), 3.18 – 3.37 (m, 3H), 1.18 – 1.40 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 173.91, 69.38, 60.55, 50.29, 47.45, 11.81, 10.96. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_3$ [M-H] $^-$: 160.09682; found: 160.09811.

***N*⁶-acetyl-*N*²,*N*²-di-ethyl-lysine (3ia)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. *N*⁶-acetyl-lysine (0.094 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3ia** (0.090 g, 75% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO_2 , EtOAc/MeOH 80:20 to 50:50).. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 4.02 – 4.13 (m, 1H), 2.96 – 3.08 (m, 4H), 2.82 – 2.96 (m, 2H), 1.97 (s, 3H), 1.70 – 1.84 (m, 1H), 1.51 – 1.70 (m, 3H), 1.25 – 1.38 (m, 2H), 1.07 – 1.24 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 181.63, 176.06, 57.47, 54.04, 49.59, 33.75, 25.86, 25.15, 24.49, 11.12. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ [M+H] $^+$: 245.18597; found: 245.18593.

***N*-isopropyl-proline (3ab)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.93 – 4.05 (m, 1H), 3.62 – 3.72 (m, 1H), 3.47 – 3.61 (m, 1H), 3.13 – 3.26 (m, 1H), 2.29 – 2.44 (m, 1H), 2.00 – 2.15 (m, 2H), 1.79 – 1.97 (m, 1H), 1.20 – 1.40 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 174.53, 65.80, 56.99, 52.28, 29.59, 23.59, 17.39, 17.26. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_2$ [M+H] $^+$: 158.11756; found: 158.11747. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (6)

***N*-isopropyl-phenylalanine (3fb):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**.

Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 6.87 – 7.24 (m, 5H), 3.24 – 3.34 (m, 1H), 2.71 – 2.80 (m, 1H), 2.45 – 2.65 (m, 2H), 0.74 – 0.93 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 181.45, 137.84, 129.08, 128.33, 126.40, 62.55, 45.96, 39.09, 22.57, 19.72. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 208.13321; found: 208.13312. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (33)

***N*-isopropyl-leucine (3eb):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O -NaOH) δ 3.08 – 3.21 (m, 1H), 2.52 – 2.66 (m, 1H), 1.37 – 1.54 (m, 1H), 1.16 – 1.35 (m, 2H), 0.86 – 1.05 (m, 6H), 0.68 – 0.86 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 177.15, 61.65, 53.02, 42.23, 27.09, 24.64, 23.83, 21.72, 20.32. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 174.14886; found: 174.14872. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (34)

***N*-isopropyl-valine (3db):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.09 – 3.20 (m, 1H), 2.82 – 2.96 (m, 1H), 1.81 – 2.00 (m, 1H), 0.99 – 1.25 (m, 6H), 0.85 – 0.98 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 181.45, 69.24, 51.18, 32.88, 23.89, 21.59, 21.17, 20.60. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 160.13321; found: 160.13307.

***N*-isopropyl-serine (3gb)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.85 – 4.01 (m, 2H), 3.72 – 3.79 (m, 1H), 3.38 – 3.52 (m, 1H), 1.24 – 1.36 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 174.36, 63.67, 62.42, 53.03, 21.26, 21.24, 20.58. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 148.09682; found: 148.09671.

***N*-isopropyl-alanine (3cb)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 3.71 – 3.80 (m, 1H), 3.38 – 3.50 (m, 1H), 1.42 – 1.53 (m, 3H), 1.26 – 1.37 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 177.76, 57.76, 52.17, 21.17, 20.71, 18.14. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 132.10191; found: 132.10181. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (35)

***N*-n-butyl-proline (3ae)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ^1H NMR of the crude mixture. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, MeOD) δ 3.78 – 3.90 (m, 1H), 3.65 – 3.78 (m, 1H), 3.15 – 3.27 (m, 1H), 2.95 – 3.15 (m, 2H), 2.30 – 2.46 (m, 1H), 1.99 – 2.15 (m, 2H), 1.82 – 1.98 (m, 1H), 1.56 – 1.76 (m, 2H), 1.30 – 1.47 (m, 2H), 0.83 – 1.04 (m, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, MeOD) δ 173.50, 70.60, 56.38, 55.95, 30.30, 28.94, 24.34, 20.88, 13.96. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$: 170.11756; found: 170.11876. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (36)

N-cyclopropylmethyl-proline (3af): Synthesized according to **General procedure**.

Proline (0.058 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3af** (0.046 g, 55% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 80:20 to 80:20). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.83 – 4.01 (m, 1H), 3.67 – 3.83 (m, 1H), 2.98 – 3.14 (m, 1H), 2.70 – 2.95 (m, 2H), 2.22 – 2.38 (m, 1H), 2.05 – 2.22 (m, 1H), 1.86 – 2.05 (m, 2H), 0.95 – 1.09 (m, 1H), 0.49 – 0.70 (m, 2H), 0.18 – 0.40 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.64, 68.63, 59.14, 53.96, 29.01, 23.06, 6.63, 4.45, 4.06. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₉H₁₄NO₂ [M-H]⁻: 168.10191; found: 168.10321.

N-(2-chloroethyl)-proline (3ag): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Proline (0.058 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3ag** (0.063 g, 71% yield). White solid was obtained after crystallization in MeOH/Et₂O. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 4.45 – 4.65 (m, 3H), 3.76 – 3.93 (m, 2H), 3.33 – 3.54 (m, 2H), 2.38 – 2.55 (m, 1H), 2.15 – 2.32 (m, 1H), 1.97 – 2.14 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 169.50, 66.38, 59.35, 46.16, 41.59, 28.06, 23.07. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₇H₁₃ClNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 178.06293; found: 178.06289.

N-benzyl-proline (3ah): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Proline (0.019 g, 0.20 mmol) affords **3ah** (0.028 g, 68% yield). White solid was obtained after crystallization in Et₂O. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.33 (br.s, 1H), 7.28 – 7.52 (m, 5H), 4.11 – 4.37 (m, 2H), 3.74 – 3.90 (m, 1H), 3.59 – 3.74 (m, 1H), 2.78 – 2.94 (m, 1H), 2.17 – 2.38 (m, 2H), 1.79 – 2.08 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.02, 130.73, 130.53, 129.40, 129.04, 67.31, 57.61, 53.31, 28.89, 22.89. HRMS (APCI+, m/z):

calculated for $C_{12}H_{16}NO_2$ $[M+H]^+$: 206.11756; found: 206.11742. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (37)

***N*-(4-chloro-benzyl)-proline (3ai)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**.

Proline (0.058 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3ai** (0.098 g, 82% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO_2 , EtOAc/MeOH 90:10 to 50:50). 1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 7.28 – 7.48 (m, 4H), 4.12 – 4.34 (m, 2H), 3.75 – 3.88 (m, 1H), 3.41 – 3.54 (m, 1H), 3.03 – 3.18 (m, 1H), 2.31 – 2.48 (m, 1H), 1.80 – 2.09 (m, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O) δ 176.56, 137.60, 134.51, 131.87, 131.63, 70.76, 59.87, 56.86, 31.30, 25.17. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $C_{12}H_{15}ClNO_2$ $[M+H]^+$: 240.07858; found: 240.07854. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (38)

***N,N*-(di-*n*-butyl)-phenylalanine (3fe)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**.

Phenylalanine (0.083 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3fe** (0.116 g, 84% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO_2 , EtOAc/MeOH 90:10 to 80:20). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 9.36 (br.s, 1H), 7.10 – 7.35 (m, 5H), 3.83 – 3.94 (m, 1H), 3.42 – 3.56 (m, 1H), 2.88 – 3.07 (m, 3H), 2.70 – 2.85 (m, 2H), 1.52 – 1.67 (m, 2H), 1.36 – 1.52 (m, 2H), 1.05 – 1.27 (m, 4H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 170.49, 137.88, 128.76, 128.55, 126.65, 67.49, 51.45, 33.82, 26.82, 19.90, 13.49. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $C_{17}H_{26}NO_2$ $[M-H]^-$: 276.19581; found: 276.19703.

***N,N*-(di-*n*-nonyl)-phenylalanine (3fj)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**.

Phenylalanine (0.083 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3fj** (0.147 g, 75% yield). White solid was

obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 50:50 to 0:100, then EtOH/MeOH 90/10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.68 (br.s, 1H), 7.13 – 7.31 (m, 5H), 3.84 – 3.93 (m, 1H), 3.50 – 3.58 (m, 1H), 2.88 – 3.05 (m, 3H), 2.67 – 2.79 (m, 2H), 1.53 – 1.67 (m, 2H), 1.38 – 1.52 (m, 2H), 0.98 – 1.35 (m, 24H), 0.75 – 0.89 (m, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.49, 138.02, 128.75, 128.59, 126.67, 67.41, 51.76, 33.71, 31.67, 29.30, 29.05, 29.03, 26.70, 25.07, 22.50, 13.94. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₂₇H₄₈NO₂ [M-H]⁻: 418.36796; found: 418.36763.

***N,N*-di-(5-hydroxypentyl)-phenylalanine (3fk)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Phenylalanine (0.083 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3fk** (0.059 g, 35% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 50:50 to 30:70). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 7.23 – 7.45 (m, 5H), 3.91 – 4.03 (m, 1H), 3.47 – 3.65 (m, 4H), 3.13 – 3.32 (m, 4H), 2.95 – 3.13 (m, 2H), 1.58 – 1.79 (m, 4H), 1.45 – 1.58 (m, 4H), 1.21 – 1.43 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 172.40, 135.73, 128.94, 128.85, 127.27, 68.29, 61.15, 33.38, 30.56, 23.33, 22.13. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₉H₃₂NO₄ [M+H]⁺: 338.23258; found: 338.23176.

***N,N*-di-*n*-nonyl-glycine (3bj)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bj** (0.149 g, 91% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 90:10 to 70:30). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.78 (br.s, 1H), 3.48 (s, 2H), 2.95 – 3.15 (m, 4H), 1.52 – 1.75 (m, 4H), 1.03 – 1.42 (m, 24H), 0.65 – 0.95 (m, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 167.42, 55.99, 53.92, 31.63, 29.26, 29.03, 28.99, 26.66, 23.71, 22.47, 13.90. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₂₀H₄₄NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 328.32155; found: 328.32095. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (38)

***N,N*-di-benzyl-glycine (3bh)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bh** (0.066 g, 52% yield). White solid was obtained after precipitation in MeOH/Et₂O. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 7.20 – 7.40 (m, 10H), 3.73 (s, 4H), 3.15 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 172.19, 139.00, 128.53, 128.24, 126.98, 56.79, 53.00. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₆H₁₈NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 256.13321; found: 256.13325. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (39)

***N*-2-butyl-glycine (3bl)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to ¹H NMR of the crude mixture. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 3.48 – 3.67 (m, 2H), 3.14 – 3.27 (m, 1H), 1.68 – 1.84 (m, 1H), 1.47 – 1.66 (m, 1H), 1.22 – 1.35 (m, 3H). 0.88 – 1.03 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 174.11, 58.44, 49.00, 28.27, 17.51, 11.47. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₆H₁₄NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 132.10191; found: 132.10181.

***N,N*-di-(*n*-pentyl)-glycine (3bm)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bm** (0.097 g, 90% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 90:10 to 70:30). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 3.68 (s, 2H), 3.05 – 3.25 (m, 4H), 1.56 – 1.80 (m, 4H), 1.20 – 1.40 (m, 8H), 0.75 – 1.00 (m, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 173.36, 58.39, 57.49, 30.46, 25.61, 24.08, 15.65. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₂H₂₆NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 216.19581; found: 216.19574.

***N*-n-pentyl-glycine (3bm')**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bm'** (0.033 g, 46% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 60:40 to 30:70). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 3.57 (s, 2H), 2.91 – 3.13 (m, 2H), 1.54 – 1.80 (m, 2H), 1.20 – 1.46 (m, 4H), 0.75 – 0.99 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 174.07, 51.74, 50.13, 30.40, 27.75, 24.05, 15.62. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₇H₁₆NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 146.11756; found: 146.11751. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (40)

***N,N*-di-*n*-dodecyl-glycine (3bn)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bn** (0.189 g, 92% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 90:10 to 70:30). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.36 (br.s, 1H), 3.49 (s, 2H), 2.95 – 3.15 (m, 4H), 1.52 – 1.75 (m, 4H), 1.03 – 1.42 (m, 36H), 0.75 – 0.95 (m, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 167.51, 56.23, 54.01, 31.80, 29.51, 29.42, 29.38, 29.23, 29.11, 26.73, 23.74, 22.57, 13.99. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₂₆H₅₄NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 412.41491; found: 412.41482.

***N*-dodecyl-glycine (3bn')**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bn'** (0.066 g, 54% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 70:30 to 40:60). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, KOH, D₂O) δ 3.00 – 3.20 (m, 2H), 2.38 – 2.58 (m, 2H), 1.36 – 1.57 (m, 2H), 1.12 – 1.35 (m, 18H), 0.73 – 0.90 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, KOH, D₂O) δ 180.96, 55.23, 51.69, 34.63, 32.69, 32.61, 32.54, 32.40, 32.22, 31.93, 30.15, 25.28, 16.42. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₄H₃₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 244.22711; found: 244.22711. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (41)

N-nonyl-glycine (3bj'): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bj'** (0.054 g, 53% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 70:30 to 40:60). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, KOH, D₂O) δ 2.90 – 3.18 (m, 2H), 2.30 – 2.56 (m, 2H), 1.28 – 1.55 (m, 2H), 1.02 – 1.38 (m, 12H), 0.65 – 0.91 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, KOH, D₂O) δ 181.71, 55.18, 51.50, 34.34, 32.09, 31.96, 31.80, 31.74, 29.78, 25.05, 16.31. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₁H₂₄NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 202.18016; found: 202.18010.

N-decyl-glycine (3bo'): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bo'** (0.075 g, 69% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 70:30 to 50:50). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, KOH, D₂O) δ 3.00 – 3.15 (m, 2H), 2.36 – 2.58 (m, 2H), 1.36 – 1.54 (m, 2H), 1.05 – 1.35 (m, 14H), 0.73 – 0.90 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, KOH, D₂O) δ 181.42, 55.34, 51.67, 34.49, 32.45, 32.30, 32.22, 32.05, 31.99, 30.04, 25.18, 16.35. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₂H₂₆NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 216.19581; found: 216.19589. The spectral data were identical to those previously reported. (40)

methyl N-tetradecylglycinate (methyl ester of 3bp': 3bp'-Me): Synthesized according to **General procedure** and **Esterification procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bp'-Me** (0.046 g, 32% yield). Pale oily compound was obtained after column chromatography. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.72 (s, 3H), 3.41 (s, 2H), 2.52 – 2.64 (m, 2H), 1.42 – 1.54 (m, 2H), 1.15 – 1.36 (m, 22H), 0.83 – 0.91 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.02, 51.71, 50.84, 49.67, 31.91, 30.04, 29.68, 29.66, 29.65, 29.64, 29.60, 29.57, 29.51, 29.34, 27.21, 22.68, 14.10. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₇H₃₆NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 286.27406; found: 286.27430.

methyl N-hexadecylglycinate (methyl ester of **3bq'**: **3bq'-Me**): Synthesized according to **General procedure** and **Esterification procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3bq'-Me** (0.059 g, 38% yield). Pale yellow, oily compound was obtained after column chromatography. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.73 (s, 3H), 3.43 (s, 2H), 2.52 – 2.64 (m, 2H), 1.42 – 1.58 (m, 2H), 1.13 – 1.37 (m, 26H), 0.80 – 0.94 (m, 3H) ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 172.71, 51.78, 50.65, 49.60, 31.92, 29.85, 29.68, 29.67, 29.65, 29.60, 29.57, 29.49, 29.35, 27.19, 22.68, 14.11. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{40}\text{NO}_2$ [M+H]⁺: 314.30536; found: 314.30540.

methyl N-octadecylglycinate (methyl ester of **3br'**: **3br'-Me**): Synthesized according to **General procedure** and **Esterification procedure**. Glycine (0.038 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3br'-Me** (0.067 g, 39% yield). Pale yellow oily compound was obtained after column chromatography. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.71 (s, 3H), 3.40 (s, 2H), 2.53 – 2.64 (m, 2H), 1.42 – 1.52 (m, 2H), 1.17 – 1.36 (m, 30H), 0.80 – 0.91 (m, 3H) ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.01, 51.68, 50.83, 49.67, 31.90, 30.04, 29.67, 29.66, 29.64, 29.59, 29.57, 29.50, 29.34, 27.21, 22.67, 14.09. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{44}\text{NO}_2$ [M+H]⁺: 342.33666; found: 342.33681.

N-dodecyl-alanine (**3cn'**): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Alanine (0.045 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3cn'** (0.063 g, 49% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO_2 , EtOAc/MeOH 70:30 to 40:60). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, KOH, D_2O) δ 3.00 – 3.20 (m, 2H), 2.38 – 2.58 (m, 2H), 1.36 – 1.57 (m, 2H), 1.12 – 1.35 (m, 18H), 0.73 – 0.90 (m, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, KOH, D_2O) δ 180.96, 55.23, 51.69, 34.63, 32.69, 32.61, 32.54, 32.40, 32.22, 31.93, 30.15, 25.28, 16.42. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{32}\text{NO}_2$ [M+H]⁺: 258.24276; found: 258.24302.

N-nonyl-proline (3aj): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Proline (0.053 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3aj** (0.063 g, 52% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 90:10 to 50:50). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.92 – 3.06 (m, 1H), 3.61 – 3.78 (m, 1H), 3.06 – 3.22 (m, 1H), 2.90 – 3.06 (m, 1H), 2.71 – 2.89 (m, 1H), 2.27 – 2.43 (m, 1H), 2.13 – 2.27 (m, 1H), 1.88 – 2.09 (m, 2H), 1.60 – 1.79 (m, 2H), 1.05 – 1.43 (m, 12H), 0.72 – 0.95 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.24, 69.66, 55.60, 54.77, 31.68, 29.38, 29.27, 29.05, 26.64, 25.66, 23.48, 22.53, 13.97. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₄H₂₈NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 242.21146; found: 242.21144.

N,N-di-ethyl-glycyl-alanine (5aa): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Quantitative yield has been obtained according to crude H NMR. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 4.08 – 4.22 (m, 1H), 3.88 – 4.03 (m, 2H), 3.17 – 3.31 (m, 4H), 1.30 – 1.36 (m, 3H), 1.21 – 1.30 (m, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 179.44, 164.77, 53.19, 51.17, 49.43, 16.92, 8.30. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₉H₁₉N₂O₃ [M+H]⁺: 203.13902; found: 203.13895.

N,N-di-(5-hydroxy-pentyl)-glycyl-alanine (5ak): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycyl-alanine (0.073 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **5ak** (0.036 g, 36% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 60:40 to 30:70). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 4.15 – 4.23 (m, 1H), 3.55 – 3.67 (m, 4H), 3.19 – 3.34 (m, 2H), 2.52 – 2.71 (m, 4H), 1.47 – 1.66 (m, 8H), 1.28 – 1.44 (m, 7H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 182.21, 175.12, 64.25, 59.67, 57.15, 53.19, 33.76, 28.20, 25.58, 20.44. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₅H₃₁N₂O₅ [M+H]⁺: 319.22275; found: 319.22278.

***N,N*-di-(*n*-dodecyl)-glycyl-alanine (5an):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Glycyl-alanine (0.073 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **5an** (0.199 g, 82% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 90:10 to 50:50). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.20 (br.s, 1H), 4.17 – 4.38 (m, 1H), 3.24 – 3.60 (m, 2H), 2.52 – 2.95 (m, 4H), 1.45 – 1.64 (m, 4H), 1.11 – 1.42 (m, 39H), 0.70 – 0.95 (m, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.93, 167.98, 56.32, 54.16, 49.95, 31.87, 29.64, 29.61, 29.58, 29.37, 29.31, 27.15, 25.34, 22.63, 18.39, 14.04. HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₂₉H₅₉N₂O₃ [M+H]⁺: 483.45202; found: 483.45170.

***N,N*-di-ethyl-glycyl-alanine (5ba):** Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Leucyl-glycyl-glycine (0.123 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **5ba** (0.101 g, 67% yield). White solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc/MeOH 60:40 to 30:70). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 3.86 – 4.02 (m, 2H), 3.75 (s, 2H), 3.38 – 3.48 (m, 1H), 2.71 – 2.88 (m, 2H), 2.46 – 2.62 (m, 2H), 1.68 – 1.83 (m, 1H), 1.32 – 1.54 (m, 2H), 0.97 – 1.13 (m, 6H), 0.83 – 0.96 (m, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O) δ 179.02, 177.83, 173.32, 64.90, 46.57, 45.81, 44.84, 40.43, 27.43, 25.57, 23.61, 14.04. HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₁₄H₂₈N₃O₄ [M+H]⁺: 302.20743; found: 302.20747.

Determination of the optical purity of products

***N*-(4-bromophenyl)-1-ethylpyrrolidine-2-carboxamide (6aa)**: According to the literature procedure (42), **6aa** was prepared from **3aa** (28.6 mg, 0.20 mmol), 4-bromoaniline (38.1 mg, 0.22 mmol), EDC•HCl (46.3 mg, 0.24 mmol), DMAP (29.3 mg, 0.24 mmol), and HOBt•H₂O (30.8 mg, 0.20 mmol), in 3ml CH₃CN under room temperature overnight. Then aq. NaHCO₃ was added, and the mixture was extracted with EtOAc 3 times. The combined organic phase was collected, concentrated under vacuo and purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 50:50 to 0:100) to afford **6aa** as a light yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.57 (s, 1H), 7.35 – 7.57 (m, 4H), 3.21 – 3.31 (m, 1H), 3.09 – 3.19 (m, 1H), 2.65 – 2.78 (m, 1H), 2.52 – 2.65 (m, 1H), 2.33 – 2.47 (m, 1H), 2.14 – 2.31 (m, 1H), 1.92 – 2.02 (m, 1H), 1.68 – 1.89 (m, 2H), 1.12 (t, *J* = 7.22 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.46, 136.84, 131.85, 120.78, 116.35, 67.61, 53.86, 49.85, 30.66, 24.39, 14.28. HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₁₃H₁₆BrN₂O [M-H]⁻: 295.04405; found: 295.04510.

HPLC measurement provide 93% (Ru) and 94% (Fe) as the *ee* values of **6aa**.

HPLC Conditions:

Column: Chiralcel OD-H, Phenomenex, Ltd.

Eluent: Heptane/isopropanol (99:1)

Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Detection: UV 232 nm

***N*-(4-bromophenyl)-2-(diethylamino)propanamide (6ca)**: According to a literature procedure (42), **6ca** was prepared from **3ca** (29.0 mg, 0.20 mmol), 4-bromoaniline (38.1 mg, 0.22 mmol), EDC•HCl (46.3 mg, 0.24 mmol), DMAP (29.3 mg, 0.24 mmol), and HOBt•H₂O (30.8 mg, 0.20 mmol), in 3ml CH₃CN under room temperature overnight. Then aq. NaHCO₃ was added, and the mixture was extracted with EtOAc 3 times. The combined organic phase was collected, concentrated under vacuo and purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 50:50 to 20:80) to afford **6ca** as a light yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.65 (s, 1H), 7.35 – 7.57 (m, 4H), 3.39 – 3.58 (m, 1H), 2.35 – 2.74 (m, 4H), 1.22 – 1.31 (m, 3H), 1.04 – 1.15 (m, 6H). HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₁₃H₂₀BrN₂O [M+H]⁺: 299.07535; found: 299.07614.

HPLC measurement provide 84% (90 °C) and 86% (60 °C) as the *ee* values of **6ca**.

HPLC Conditions

Column: Chiralcel OD-H, Phenomenex, Ltd.

Eluent: Heptane/isopropanol (99:1)

Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Detection: UV 254s nm

Methyl diethylphenylalaninate (6fa): According to a literature procedure (44), **6fa** was prepared from **3fa**. To a stirred solution of the **3fa** (44.2 mg, 0.2 mmol) in toluene/MeOH (1/1 ml), TMSCHN₂ (0.4 mmol, 2M in toluene) was added. The mixture was stirred for 1h at room temperature and concentrated in vacuo to give **6fa** as transparent oil. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.12 – 7.40 (m, 5H), 3.64 – 3.74 (m, 1H), 3.65 (s, 3H), 3.06 – 3.17 (m, 1H), 2.89 – 3.02 (m, 1H), 2.75 – 2.89 (m, 2H), 2.52 – 2.65 (m, 2H), 1.08 (t, *J* = 7.17 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.06, 138.68, 129.21, 128.18, 126.20, 64.95, 51.04, 44.50, 35.99, 13.66. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported. (45)

HPLC measurement provide 97% (Ru) and 72% (Fe) as the *ee* values of **6fa**.

HPLC Conditions

Column: Chiralcel OZ-H, Phenomenex, Ltd.

Eluent: Heptane/isopropanol (99.7:0.3)

Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Detection: UV 190 nm

2-(diethylamino)-3-hydroxy-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)propanamide (6ga): According to a literature procedure (42), **6ga** was prepared from **3ga** (32.0 mg, 0.20 mmol), 4-methoxyaniline (27 mg, 0.22 mmol), EDC•HCl (46.3 mg, 0.24 mmol), NEt₃ (56 ul, 0.4 mmol), and HOBt•H₂O (30.8 mg, 0.20 mmol), in 3ml CH₃CN under room temperature overnight. Then aq. NaHCO₃ was added, the mixture was extracted with EtOAc 3 times. The combined organic phase was collected, concentrated under vacuo and purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 50:50 to 20:80) to afford **6ga** as a light yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.42 (s, 1H), 7.40 – 7.50 (m, 2H), 6.83 – 6.92 (m, 2H), 4.02 – 4.10 (m, 1H), 3.81 – 3.89 (m, 1H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 3.48 – 3.57 (m, 1H), 2.56 – 2.82 (m, 4H), 1.14 (t, *J* = 7.07 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.45, 130.40, 121.15, 114.21, 101.59, 63.98, 58.56, 55.48, 44.87, 14.11. HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₁₄H₂₃N₂O₃ [M+H]⁺: 267.17032; found: 267.17031.

HPLC measurement provide 86% as the *ee* value of **6ga**.

HPLC Conditions

Column: Chiralcel OD-H, Phenomenex, Ltd.

Eluent: Heptane/isopropanol (97:3)

Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Detection: UV 250 nm

2-(diethylamino)-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-methylbutanamide (6da): Compound **6da** was prepared from **3da** (35.0 mg, 0.20 mmol), 4-methoxyaniline (27 mg, 0.22 mmol), COMU (43) (257 mg, 0.60 mmol) and *N,N*-Diisopropylethylamine (70 μ l, 0.4 mmol) in 1ml DMF, under room temperature stirring for 1h. Then DMF was removed under vacuo and the residual mixture was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 50:50 to 20:80) to afford **6da** as a light yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.58 (br.s, 1H), 7.40 – 7.53 (m, 2H), 6.79 – 6.90 (m, 2H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 2.91 – 3.12 (m, 1H), 2.58 – 2.80 (m, 4H), 2.12 – 2.28 (m, 1H), 1.09 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 3H), 1.00 – 1.07 (m, 6H), 0.98 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H). HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₁₆H₂₇N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺: 279.20670; found: 279.20673.

HPLC measurement provide 99% as the *ee* value of **6da**.

HPLC Conditions

Column: Chiralcel OD-H, Phenomenex, Ltd.

Eluent: Heptane/isopropanol (98:2)

Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Detection: UV 250 nm

2-(diethylamino)-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylpentanamide (6ea): According to a literature procedure (42), **6ea** was prepared from **3ea** (37.4 mg, 0.20 mmol), 4-methoxyaniline (27 mg, 0.22 mmol), EDC•HCl (46.3 mg, 0.24 mmol), NEt₃ (56 μ l, 0.4 mmol), and HOBt•H₂O (30.8 mg, 0.20 mmol), in 3ml CH₃CN under room temperature overnight. Then aq. NaHCO₃ was added, the mixture was extracted with EtOAc 3 times. The combined organic phase was concentrated under vacuo and purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 50:50 to 20:80) to afford **6ea** as a light yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.44 (s, 1H), 7.42 – 7.52 (m, 2H), 6.79 – 6.91 (m, 2H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 3.30 – 3.43 (m, 1H), 2.38 – 2.75 (m, 4H), 1.73 – 1.98 (m, 2H), 1.28 – 1.37 (m, 1H), 1.06 – 1.15 (m, 6H), 0.95 – 1.01 (m, 3H), 0.90 – 0.95 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR

(100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.95, 131.42, 125.62, 120.66, 114.12, 55.48, 44.48, 34.47, 26.43, 23.44, 21.98, 13.79. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₄H₂₃N₂O₃ [M+H]⁺: 293.22235; found: 293.22245.

HPLC measurement provide 99% (Ru) and 80% (Fe) as the *ee* values of **6ea**.

HPLC Conditions

Column: Chiralcel OD-H, Phenomenex, Ltd.

Eluent: Heptane/isopropanol (99:1)

Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Detection: UV 250 nm

HPLC traces

Racemic 6aa (from racemic 3aa) <Chromatogram>

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 232nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
22,185	21,760	24,341	49,991
26,781	26,187	30,656	50,009
			100,000

Enantiomer **6aa** (from **S-3aa** with Ru)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 232nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
22.893	22.283	25.419	96.575
28.227	27.499	29.611	3.425
			100,000

Enantiomer **6aa** (from **S-3aa** with Fe)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 232nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
22.630	22.229	27.648	96.803
28.214	27.765	29.984	3.197
			100,000

Racemic **6ca** (from racemic **3ca**)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 254nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
16,960	16,416	18,421	49,966
19,806	19,211	21,504	50,034
			100,000

Enantiomer **6ca** (from **S-3ca**, 90°C)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 254nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
16,484	15,957	17,824	7,952
19,116	18,496	21,621	92,048
			100,000

Enantiomer **6ca** (from **S-3ca**, 60°C)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 254nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
16,406	15,829	17,589	7,212
19,037	18,432	21,173	92,788
			100,000

Racemic **6fa** (from racemic **3fa**)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 190nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
18,130	17,205	18,965	51,768
19,905	19,029	21,493	48,232
			100,000

Enantiomer **6fa** (from **S-3fa** with Ru)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 190nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
17,413	16,480	19,200	98,597
19,975	19,264	20,629	1,403
			100,000

Enantiomer **6fa** (from **S-3fa** with Fe)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 226nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
15,989	15,275	17,216	86,014
17,794	17,216	19,200	13,986
			100,000

Racemic **6ga** (from racemic **3ga**)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 250nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
42,531	41,525	44,299	48,989
45,110	44,299	50,080	51,011
			100,000

Enantiomer **6ga** (from **S-3ga**)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 250nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
41,770	40,736	42,571	6,970
43,142	42,571	50,560	93,030
			100,000

Racemic **6da** (from racemic **3da**)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 250nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
23,653	22,997	24,789	49,464
25,424	24,789	27,296	50,536
			100,000

Enantiomer **6da** (from **S-3d**)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 250nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
23,846	23,275	24,544	0,259
25,239	24,544	27,776	99,741
			100,000

Racemic **6ea** (from racemic **3ea**)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 250nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
20,214	19,648	21,675	49,893
28,952	28,117	31,040	50,107
			100,000

Enantiomer **6ea** (from **S-3ea** with Ru)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 250nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
20,226	19,605	21,227	0,733
28,361	27,829	31,328	99,267
			100,000

Enantiomer **6ea** (from **S-3ea** with Fe)

<Chromatogram>

mAU

<Peak Table>

AD2

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%

PDA Ch1 250nm

Ret. Time	Peak Start	Peak End	Area%
21,771	20,885	22,891	10,128
31,253	30,293	33,493	89,872
			100,000

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra

3aa

3ba

3ca

3da

3ea

ty1211-cr-proton2

3fa

3ga

3ia

3ab

3cb

3db

3eb

ty1244-NaOH

ty1302

3fb

3gb

ty1409-proton

ty1409-carbon

3ae

3af

3ag

ty1304

ty1304

3ah

3ai

3fe

3fk

3fj

3bl

3bh

3bm

3bm'

3bj

3bn

3bj'

3bo'

3bn'

3bp'-Me, Methyl ester of 3bp'

3bq'-Me, Methyl ester of **3bq'**

3br'-Me, Methyl ester of **3br'**

3cn'

3aj

5aa

5an

5ak

5ba

